

STADIEM

STARTUP DRIVEN INNOVATION IN EUROPEAN MEDIA

D4.4 INTEGRATE AND PHASE PHASES REPORT - THE 2ND CYCLE

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Abstract	This document covers the activities related to the Integrate phase and Pilot phase in the second cycle of the STADIEM Acceleration Programme (February-September 2023, involving the selected start-ups/scale-ups from the 2 nd cohort (12 in Integrate, 6 in Pilot). Besides providing a detailed account of the activities, the document contains an assessment of each of the Phases and identifies lessons learned for future program deployment.
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* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

STADIEM is a start-up/scale-up to corporate program aiming to foster the development of next generation internet solutions for the media sector. Its innovation program supports a co-creation trajectory between a start-up and scale-up and a (media) corporate and facilitates the upscaling process of the start-up/scale-up via training, mentorship and showcasing at events. The STADIEM Innovation Program is built in two cycles that each have 4 phases: Match, Develop, Integrate and Pilot. The first cycle ran from April 2021 till September 2022. In this report we present the activities, results and insights of the Integration and Pilot Phases between February 2023 and September 2023. It thus builds upon the previous report that covered these topics for the Match and Develop Phase of the 2nd cycle (see D4.3 'Match and Develop phases report, the 2nd cycle').

Results and outcomes Integrate and Pilot Phases 2nd cycle.

After the selection process that closed the previous OC2 Develop phase, the third Phase of the STADIEM program, the Integrate Phase, was launched. Out of the 16 that participated in the Develop Phase and its evaluation stage, 12 were chosen to continue the program. The main goal of the Integrate phase for the beneficiaries is to integrate their solution on a technical or service level with their corporate, in what can be described as a "pre-pilot" or "private pilot", in order to be ready for a public pilot in the last phase of the program. This achievement is demonstrated by submitting final budget and review reports at the end of the phase, to be reviewed by four external experts, as well as participating in a remote evaluation as part of the final selection procedure for the following Pilot Phase.

This third Phase of the STADIEM program began on 13. February 2023 with a joint Kick-off event. The purpose of this event was to introduce the STADIEM framework for this specific Phase and provide more information about the Integrate Phase. It also served as an activity towards community building and as a Q&A session for the start-ups.

In the second cycle of the STADIEM program, six top-performing start-ups from the Integrate phase joined the Pilot Phase, an increase from four in OC1. This expansion was made possible by reallocating unspent third-party funding from the Match OC2 Phase budget, contingent on the additional start-ups meeting quality criteria and contributing to program visibility and impact. The second cycle's Pilot Phase kicked off with an onboarding meeting on 2nd May 2023, introducing the framework and expectations to six selected scale-ups. They submitted pilot proposals and were paired with mother hubs for support. During the phase, they executed public pilots, showcased results, and participated in events like Future Week, MCO Mediatech Festival, and Latitude59. Midway, a mid-term review and financial report were conducted, leading to a final evaluation at the end of the phase. Start-ups presented their achievements in a final investment committee meeting and showcased their work at IBC2023 as the closing event.

To implement the lessons learned from the OC1 Integrate and Pilot Phases, various measures for improvement were identified that were put into effect during the remaining phases of this 2nd cycle and will be useful for potential future cycles as well. For the Pilot Phase, one example is that we planned to have more events at the start of the phase, to avoid the summer holiday, and maximize the showcasing activities in the awkwardly timed phase.

When comparing the Integrate Phase of the 2nd cycle with the same phase of the first cycle, one can conclude that having Airtable as STADIEM's tool of communication from the beginning of the cycle was highly beneficial. The communication of the phase improved information flow and issue solving in a significant way. It also improves in terms of efficiency and clarity, and

benefits all the start-ups, because of the public announcements and “Issue tracker” solution to answer questions publicly.

For the Integrate Phase, as with the 1st cycle, the KPI's for beginning of the phase (min 12) and for ending of the phase (min 4 to choose) were met. Two of the 12 Integrate beneficiaries fulfilled all procedures for participating in the final stage of the selection procedure for the pilot phase but declined the invitation for the Investment Committee Board meeting. For the Pilot phase OC2, STADIEM managed to select and let start 6 beneficiaries from the 10 beneficiaries that declared to candidate for the public pilot phase and at least 6 of them have set up public pilot executions. Due to these public pilots, the six beneficiaries managed to acquire new business leads, investor leads, and client leads. They also participated, besides the STADIEM organized demo-event, at various events organized by STADIEM (Latitude59, MediaCityOdense MediaTech Festival, Future Week, IBC) (see also D1.7 'Report on the community building activities, v3' and D5.9 'Outreach and impact creation activities v3').

As for OC1, the overall result of the first cycle of the STADIEM Innovation Program at the end of September 2022 is that, for each 4 phases, all KPI's of minimum participation at the beginning of the phase and minimum selection at the end of the phase were always met. A breach of cooperation between a corporate and a beneficiary never happened during a phase and during the entire first cycle of the program and only once in the second.

Budget and grant distribution Integrate and Pilot phases 2nd cycle.

Each of the Integrate and Pilot phase beneficiaries could receive a maximum grant of 27.500€ for the Integrate Phase and 50.000 euro for the Pilot Phase, covering personnel costs, consumables, travel and training and marketing and communication costs.

The foreseen third-party support funding budget was in both phases (330.000€ Integrate, 300.000€ Pilot) almost consumed totally (99% in the case of Integration; 100% in the case of Piloting) by the participating beneficiaries.

Running the program and providing upscaling support in Integrate and Pilot 2nd cycle.

As observed in the previous Phases reports of the first and second cycle (see D4.1 for OC1 Match and Develop, D4.2 for OC1 Integrate and Pilot and D4.3 for OC2 Match and Develop), on an operational level, STADIEM managed to organize 2 highly qualitative cycles. The program framework still had a very intense rhythm in both phases, which allowed it to follow a consistent pace within the innovation track and enabled the beneficiaries to engage their corporate time in the process.

The four mother hubs provided the necessary support and mentoring based on individual needs of the beneficiaries and facilitated leads in their networks. Training in the Integration Phase was organized as early as possible to let the beneficiaries be fully aware of the fast pace of the phase, the challenges of the activities, the expectations, and the result to be achieved. The main mandatory activity was a 3-day “Bootcamp”, consisting of a masterclass led by two experts, followed by 2 days of 1-to-1 meetings between each beneficiary and one of the experts. These meetings were prepared ahead by each party and were tailored to each beneficiary's specificities and needs.

During the Pilot phase, STADIEM organized events to showcase the demos of the 6 final beneficiaries (Future Week, IBC 2023) and provided other opportunities for demonstrating the solutions. Besides these STADIEM events, the 6 pilot beneficiaries also took their own initiatives with their grant to showcase their solutions at relevant venues in Europe.

Learnings and future perspectives for Integrate and Pilot phases.

While the STADIEM Innovation program generated qualitative results both in terms of outcomes and in terms of program management overall, this does not mean that there are no lessons to be learned to improve the program for after the 2nd Cycle.

The OC2 Integrate Phase has implemented the lessons learned from OC1, mostly in time management, training, and evaluation of the start-ups. The OC1 Integrate phase was very short, and an intensive period for the start-ups, hubs, and consortium, paired with an overlap with the OC2 Match Phase. The start-ups had limited time for training, and deviations in spending could have been expected in the next cycle. In OC2, training has been upgraded (from a one-day masterclass to a 3-day “Bootcamp”), and feedback from external experts helped improve the evaluation process and reporting procedures for a more efficient process. Reporting for start-ups and corporate has also been made available early in the Phase to streamline it better. The positive outcomes and improved efficiency of the program proved that the lessons learned from OC1 were pertinent, and that the strategy in place to implement improvements was fruitful. Feedback from start-ups, corporate and external experts stressed very little to improve during OC2, besides even more streamlined reporting, which is possible through the Airtable toolkit.

Feedback from the end-of-phase survey in the Pilot Phase indicates that the STADIEM program was generally well-received by the Pilot Phase start-ups, providing valuable exposure, networking, and financial support. While the program's flexibility and exposure opportunities were appreciated, areas for improvement included streamlining reporting processes. To address timing issues during the summer for the Pilot Phase, the consortium organized showcasing events at the start of the Pilot Phase and included the IBC2023 event after the official phase end, which received positive feedback from start-ups and improved participation compared to the previous cycle. This feedback underscores the need for ongoing refinement of reporting procedures in the program and highlights the importance of accommodating diverse industry needs in future cycles.

To fully cover both phases (Pilot OC2 ended in September 2023) and to include a thorough reflection of both phases, the due date of this deliverable D4.4 was delayed from its initial submission in July 2023 (M34) to September 2023 (M36).

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ABBREVIATIONS

AB	Advisory Board
AMA	Ask Me Anything
IC	Investment Committee
ICM	Investment Committee Meeting
LOI	Letter of Intent
WP	Work package
MCB	Media City Bergen
NMA	Next Media Accelerator
STK	Storytek
VRT	Vlaamse Radio- en Televisieomroeporganisatie
OC	Open Call

1. INTRODUCTION

This report details the activities performed and lessons learned during the Integrate and Pilot phases of the 2nd cycle of the STADIEM innovation Program. The report outlines the transition from the 12 beneficiaries selected from the Develop phase to the 6 selected to the Pilot phase. The document is structured in a manner that initially tackles the Integrate Phase followed by the final Pilot Phase.

The primary objective of WP4 'STADIEM Innovation Program' is to implement the innovation program around the framework designed in WP2 '*STADIEM incubation and acceleration framework*', following the selection of start-ups in WP3 '*Engaging start-ups/SMEs*'. The STADIEM program contains 2 cycles of four phases, each corresponding to a specific task in WP4 namely Match (T4.1), Develop (T4.2), Integrate (T4.3) and Pilot (T4.4). The previous two phases and tasks of the 2nd cycle included the Match Phase and Develop Phase, and their implementation, outcomes and insights are addressed in the report "*D4.3 Match and Develop Phases - The 2nd Cycle*" submitted in M31 (April 2023).

The report opens with a description and objectives of the Integrate Phase (Chapter 2), followed by a comprehensive presentation of the Integrate Phase Framework for the 2nd cycle (Chapter 3). Both chapters have the same outline in six sections. Section one is a description of the phase with a presentation of the participants and the objectives. Section two provides a presentation of the phase framework for the 1st cycle, including an overview of the timeline, an overview of the training and upskilling activities, the evaluation and selection process and the organised networking and showcasing events. Section 3 presents the budget rules and the total amount of reimbursements requested by the beneficiaries compared to the total grant available in the phase. Section 4 discusses the KPI's, and results achieved while section 5 presents any deviation from the phase planning and any corrective action taken. Finally, Section 6 highlights lessons learned and suggests improvement opportunities for both phases during the 2nd cycle of STADIEM.

Because the Pilot phase of the 2nd cycle only ended in September 2023, this report was submitted with a slight delay of two weeks, allowing the hubs on the one hand to finalise their obligations to the beneficiaries and on the other hand to gather the data and insights for the Pilot phase.

2. INTEGRATE PHASE

The Integrate Phase OC2 (Task T4.3) ran from 13th February 2023 to 23 April 2023 and was led by Storytek and all three other innovation hubs contributed to the activity.

Task	Name	Lead	Contributing Partners	Timing
T4.3	Integrate	Storytek	NMA, MCB, VRT	February 2023 - April 2023

TABLE 1: OVERVIEW INTEGRATE PHASE 2ND CYCLE

From the 16 STADIEM beneficiaries that started the previous Develop Phase OC2 and applied for the Integrate Phase OC2, 12 beneficiaries with their own solution and STADIEM project with a EU media corporate were selected for the Integrate Phase. Table 2 below provides an overview of the 12 STADIEM Integrate projects.

Beneficiary	STADIEM Project	Corporate Partner(s)	Mother Hub
BotTalk	Their technology focuses on text-to-speech, allowing publishing houses with an average output of 200 news articles a day to create 8 to 30 hours of audio daily from it. Funke, NOZ, t-online, VRT, Mediafin and Roularta all partnered-up with BotTalk, leading to piloting their solution for training unique AI voices of superior quality in smaller languages like Flemish.	VRT, Mediafin, Roularta, FunkeMedia, Ströer, NOZ	VRT
Dcipher Analytics	In today's globalised world, journalists are confronted with a continuous influx of information, which requires them to manage enormous volumes of text. To address this challenge, Dcipher Analytics is currently testing its platform in STADIEM in collaboration with Omni's editors. This platform aims to provide journalists with a comprehensive overview of news and enable them to focus on specific areas of interest in greater detail.	Omni	STK
Druid Learning	A white-label educational content e-commerce platform designed with inclusiveness in mind, allowing publishers to control, manage and distribute their digital content directly to their end users. They have partnered with the corporate partner of CJ Fallon Irish Educational Publisher, which is looking into improving and optimising content production through automation processes.	CJ Fallon	STK

Einbliq.io	Broadcasters and OTT companies are facing ever-growing streaming costs, mainly paid to Content Delivery Networks (CDN). With an all-embracing data analytics suite, einbliq.io, helps media companies delivering excellent and quality assured streaming services at lower cost. Working with them in this phase is RBB, on linear broadcasting and audience measurement, which will also explore streaming and energy consumption, with support from ARTE.	RBB + ARTE	NMA
IZI Records	Broadcasting organisations such as CCMA are actively exploring alternative solutions to enhance the quality and collaborative creation of the surging volume of user-generated content. As part of STADIEM, IZI Record was developed to merge UGC signals with broadcasting signals from TV3. This is achieved through the utilisation of Orange Spain's 5G network, which provides broadcasters with an immersive environment for interacting with their audience during live events.	CCMA	NMA
Levelr	Trends indicate a transition from open networks to closed platforms such as Discord and Telegram, thereby presenting new challenges for music labels such as Warner Music Group and Sony Music Entertainment to evaluate fan engagement. In the context of STADIEM, Levelr has developed a platform that sits atop the Discord servers of Sony MG and WMG. This platform is designed to translate chat data into more comprehensive customer engagement analytics, thereby enabling music labels to effectively evaluate fan engagement.	Sony MG, WMG	NMA
Limecraft	Their cloud-based collaboration platform 'Limecraft Flow' is used by media producers worldwide to manage their workflow, allowing them to create more content faster. Built-in AI allows automation of several steps in the production process – including raw material processing, audio transcription and subtitling – finding a corporate partner in VRT, which needed to optimize their increased video production workload.	VRT	VRT

Media Distillery	In the highly competitive streaming industry, on-demand provider NLZIET recognizes the significance of delivering captivating viewing experiences. As part of STADIEM, Media Distillery has collaborated with NLZIET to integrate its machine learning (ML) techniques into the provider's platform. This integration enables the automated generation of content chapters and titles that facilitate seamless navigation and enhance the overall streaming experience.	NLZIET	STK
Rumble Studio	The creation of compelling audio-based content such as podcasts demands substantial resources from the pharma network Havas Health & You (HH&Y). In response to this challenge, Rumble Studios has partnered with HH&Y as part of STADIEM to offer online asynchronous interview forms. These forms enable the network to conduct remote interviews of patients and large groups of people in an ad hoc manner, without compromising on quality or quantity.	Havas Health & You	NMA
Scriptix	A full-service speech recognition provider featuring an ecosystem of (custom) speech-to-text models and additional services, aimed at enabling everybody to turn spoken word into text. Roularta Media Group is their partner in the STADIEM program, working with them on empowering transcription services with a focus on smaller language areas such as Flemish and Belgian French.	Roularta	MCB
Television.ai	AI to unlock insights from raw video footage (such as common objects, sentiments, emotions, faces, well-known people, topics, etc.) to be used for SEO, archive indexing, and even automatically create edits featuring synthetic voice over: matching with the needs of their corporate partner RBB.	RBB	MCB
Textgain	Due to the shift of discussions to social media platforms, content producers such as Mediahuis have been experiencing a decline in both debate and revenue. As part of STADIEM, Textgain's technology has been integrated into GZA and De Standaard articles to encourage readers to actively participate in discourse in a toxic free environment. To develop this solution, Textgain has also partnered with Tree Company and Wienu.	Mediahuis	MCB

TABLE 2: THE 12 PROJECTS OF THE INTEGRATE 2ND CYCLE

2.1 DESCRIPTIONS AND OBJECTIVES

The 16 Develop Phase OC2 beneficiaries got a first introduction to the major lines of the phase in December 2022 as part of the preparatory work for the phase.

After the 12 selected start-ups/scale-ups accepted their invitation to the third phase of the 2nd cycle of the acceleration program, STADIEM launched the Integrate Phase with a kick-off event explaining the objectives and timeline with major milestones and events. During this phase, the selected companies were invited to move forward with their pre-existing developments and to participate in events organized by the 4 hubs VRT, MCB, STK, and NMA to finalize and “pre-pilot” their solutions developed with their corporate partners. Each beneficiary was eligible to receive up to €27,500 to cover their expenses during the Integrate Phase, as it was also the case in the OC1 the previous year.

The primary objective of the Integrate Phase was for the start-ups/scale-ups to integrate their solution in close collaboration with their corporate’s needs, as well as respecting STADIEM’s timeline and guidelines.

The 12 start-ups were, as for the previous phases, evenly distributed among the consortium partners. This resulted in every hub acting as the mother hub of contact, to 3 start-ups each. Table 3 shows the allocation of beneficiaries to mother hubs.

<p><u>VRT</u> Bottalk Druid Learning Limecraft</p>	<p><u>STK/MT</u> einbliq.io Dcipher Analytics Media Distillery</p>
<p><u>MCB</u> Scriptix Television.AI Textgain</p>	<p><u>NMA</u> Levellr IZI Records Rumble Studio</p>

TABLE 3: ALLOCATION OF BENEFICIARIES OVER MOTHER HUBS

2.2 FRAMEWORK

- 2.2.1 Overview of the timeline

The Integrate Phase began with a joint kick-off meeting to introduce the upcoming steps expected from the beneficiaries in this new time frame of 2 months, compared with the 6 months of Develop Phase. It also gave an overview of the specific goals for the Phase, and what is meant by pre-piloting. Emphasis was also made on developing a contract with a corporate partner and expanding leads and business sustainability after a phase of primarily developing their solutions.

Different to the 1st cycle, the 2nd batch of STADIEM start-ups attended what was named a “bootcamp” over 3 days, virtually. Given the short length of the Phase, no travel was expected from the start-ups as part of mandatory common activities.

Each beneficiary was allocated to a mother hub as explained above, which they had check-ins with and whom they could ask for general organizational questions.

At the end of the Integrate Phase, participants had to formally apply for the Pilot Phase using an application form. External and internal evaluators followed a two-step selection process to choose the 4 to 6 teams to proceed to the Pilot Phase. First, external evaluators assessed the application and rated the beneficiaries in order of which they were deemed suitable to move forward to the next Phase. Secondly during the investment committee meeting a pitch session followed before the four innovation hubs. Based on the composite score of experts and hub experts, the 6 highest-ranked scale-ups were invited to the Pilot Phase.

Date	Activity	Description
15 December 2022	First introduction to the Phase	Online joint event for the Develop Phase start-ups and the 4 hubs to get familiar with the upcoming phase
13 February	Kick off meeting	Online event lead by Storytek to describe the expected outcomes, processes and deadlines and upcoming Action Plan
14-22 February	Action Plan	Start-ups submit their Action Plan for the Integrate Phase on Airtable
28 Feb - 2 March	Integrate Phase "Bootcamp"	Online mandatory 3-day event with 2 experts to understand and tackle challenges specific to the Integrate Phase
13 - 18 March	Light Mid-Term Check-In	1-on-1 informal meeting between start-ups and their mother hub to follow-up on their progress, collaboration with their corporate, and answer specific questions
19 April	Proposal Deadline	Deadline for start-ups and corporate to submit their reports on Airtable
20-25 April	External experts' evaluation	4 external experts review both start-ups and their corporate's reports and pre-rank them before the final evaluation meeting
26 April	Finalizing Evaluation by innovation hubs	The 4 hubs evaluate the start-ups' presentation + answers to questions and select the best 6 start-ups

TABLE 4: FRAMEWORK AND TIMELINE INTEGRATE PHASE 2ND CYCLE

- 2.2.2 Introductory event to the Integrate Phase

Unlike during the OC1 Develop Phase, the OC2 Integrate Phase, together with the Pilot Phase, was already introduced during the Develop Phase on 15 December 2022 during a 60 min online event. The goal was to explain the major lines and objectives of the Phase for the first time, followed by a Q&A.

The presentation tackled:

- Goals and expectations: regarding results and reports
- Timeline and important dates: key milestones and events, as well as deadlines for reports

- A description of the upcoming activities: as described in the Guide of Applicants
- The evaluation process: action plan, budget report, corporate report, and experts review, finishing with the Investment Committee Meeting
- A conclusion about Integrate to Pilot final selection and date of kick-off.

It was followed by an introduction to the Pilot Phase, and the start-ups were able to conclude with a Q&A regarding both Phases. It allowed them to understand the expectations from Develop to Integrate, as well as the overall timeline of the project ahead of the Develop Phase evaluation period. It was also organized to anticipate the difficulties and challenges that the start-ups could face later in the project and to de-risk, because the Integrate Phase lasts for only 3 months and contains phase specific challenges that are new and potentially unexpected for start-ups and scaleups.

The start-ups did not go over the allocated time for the Q&A and Storytek (and MCB for Pilot Phase) had enough time to cover all the questions, before encouraging the start-ups to follow-up with addressing later issues via the 'issue tracker' module on the STADIEM's Airtable communication and management platform.

- 2.2.3 Kick-off Event

The 2nd open call of the Integrate Phase commenced on 13 February 2023 with a joint Kick-off event organized by Storytek, which aimed to celebrate the new Phase's start and introduce the STADIEM Integrate framework.

The event was a 90 min online event hosted at Storytek in Tallinn. Sten Saluveer and Tiphaine Vigniel gave introductions to the Integrate program framework and the activities during the Phase, respectively. The presentation was followed by a Q&A session, where start-ups were able to ask questions that were not answered during the first presentation of the Phase, during the Develop Phase, on the 15th December 2022.

Unlike during the beginning of the OC1 Integrate Phase in 2022, the start-ups were already familiar with the project management tool Airtable used for STADIEM's announcements and communication between hubs and start-ups by MCB's Kristian Bruarøy. The transition between Develop and Integrate was therefore easier during the OC2, as there was no significant change in the framework and tool usage.

The amounts of questions during the Q&A fit into the time limit, but start-ups were also encouraged to fill out any additional remark or question in the according section mentioned above - the "Issue Tracker", on Airtable. It can cover not only specific questions, but also matters that might concern everybody and that would benefit from being asked publicly, as opposed to a one-to-one meeting with the mother hub.

During the kickoff, the start-ups were reminded to provide their action plans a week after the event. The Q&A also provided guidance regarding this action plan, to be submitted via Airtable and describing the start-ups' objectives, strategy and budget plan.

- 2.2.4 Networking and Event

Storytek: One 3-day online masterclass “Bootcamp”

The beneficiaries were invited to attend one main online event: a 3-day “Bootcamp + Ask Me Anything”, followed by two days of 1-to-1 meetings, where each startup could meet each expert separately for personalized advice.

The experts / speakers that day were:

- **Guido Van Nispen:** he is the CEO & Co-Founder of [Insiber.com](https://www.insiber.com), an independent one-stop SaaS support platform empowering SME cybersafety and insurance. He has many years of executive management, advisory, and supervisory experience in the technology, finance, and media sectors. His positions include CEO of Dutch national news agency ANP, Managing Director of investment funds V-Ventures & Dutch Creative Industry Fund, Publisher of Future of Work foundation i4j, and Executive Director at British Telecom. His advisory and supervisory board experience includes purpose-driven commercial and non-profit organizations, including Triodos, World Press Photo, Cinekid, Amsterdam Crossmediaweek, IPAN, New Markets Venture Partners, People Centered Internet, and AVROTROS.
- **Sebastien Toupy:** a community builder, storyteller, and strategist with a strong passion for start-ups, technology, and social impact. Throughout his career, Sebastien Toupy has dedicated his time to designing programs and events that help startup founders build successful, inclusive, and sustainable ventures. Sebastien Toupy's dedication to promoting entrepreneurship and social impact has led him to support several organizations actively working to promote these goals, such as The NEXT Web (where he was leading corporate venture building), SXSW, The Venture by Chivas, EU Commission, Seedstars, Startup Chile, Innofest, Impact Hub, Tech2Impact, Startup wise guys, Make Sense, and Decelera.

The masterclass included the following topics:

- How scale-ups and corporates can integrate their technology stacks without disrupting existing processes.
- Common challenges faced during integration and how to overcome them.
- How to manage stakeholder expectations during the pre-piloting phase.
- Misconceptions that need to be addressed before integration.
- How scale-ups and corporate can negotiate mutually beneficial terms, navigate decision-making processes, and engage with C-level executives.

The 1-to-1 meetings were over a 2-day period, on the 1 and 2 March 2023. The two experts were previously given each beneficiary pitch deck to study, for personalized advice. A Google form was created for the 1 to 1 meetings schedule of each expert. The settings were private and only included the founders and one expert per session. They were slots of 40 min each, for a total of 80 min of individual training for each startup.

11 out of 12 start-ups attended the whole 3-day Bootcamp (One startup could not attend the group event, however justified their absence and attended the 1 to 1) The attendance was tracked on Airtable in a specific section where start-ups filled-out a detailed attendance form.

Feedback was then provided by each expert to STADIEM: both wrote a report on a Google Form previously used during the meetings, on their overall impressions regarding the start-ups, their challenges and key points to improve to make it to the Pilot Phase and increase their chances of succeeding in the future. A significant percentage of the start-ups focused too much on their solutions, compared to their business cases, and needed further guidance regarding how to negotiate their contracts, financial sustainability, and communication with the right stakeholders at corporate.

DTS

Geneva March 2023

- 2.2.5 Evaluation and Selection Process

During the Integrate Phase, start-ups and scale-ups were required to fulfil certain specific criteria to proceed to the Pilot Phase. They were first introduced during the first introductory meeting in December 2022, then explained more in detail during the kick-off meeting and individually during the lightweight mid-term meeting between each startup and their mother hubs. The start-ups were expected to justify their spendings in a budget report, then fill out an overall activity report, both via Airtable, describing their progress, but also the consistency regarding what was announced in their action plans, submitted at the beginning of the Phase.

The evaluation process was a three-step process and involved three parties:

Firstly, start-ups filled out their budget and general reports on Airtable. The questionnaire was made available on 15 March, to allow each startup time to organize their schedules to fill it out in as many times as needed. It included an Impact Assessment section, like during the Develop Phase evaluation report. The deadline was 19 April 2023, End of Business (6.00PM CET). At the same time, corporates filled out a questionnaire separately from start-ups, to evaluate the scale-ups progress, objectives, performances, and communication. It was filled out after communicating with start-ups, but it was mandatory that each questionnaire (start-ups' and corporate's) were filled out separately and without influence. It was also available from the 15th March 2023 and the deadline was also the same as the scale-ups questionnaire: 19. April, 2023, EOB (6.00PM CET).

Out of the 12 applicants, 12 succeeded in submitting all necessary documents for applying to the next phase. One beneficiary announced prior to the evaluation process by external experts that it was no longer a candidate for selection for the Pilot Phase due to scaling and growing. Another beneficiary announced shortly before the hub evaluation meeting in the evaluation process that they withdraw their application for the Pilot Phase, claiming that they thought its project was not strong enough. One beneficiary had in the document submission phase before the evaluation by external experts' issues that lead to a pivot and wanted to add a new corporate to the pre-existing one to manage its pilot (and STADIEM project objectives). After concertation with the consortium, it was agreed to accept the pivot on the conditions they kept complying with the Guide of Applicant and with their Sub Grant Agreement (hence execute the work with the initial corporate) and would complete the questionnaires in time. They successfully complied to both criteria and were selected for the evaluation round.

Secondly, four external experts/evaluators were selected to evaluate the questionnaires and give a preliminary ranking of the start-ups, ahead of the Investment Committee Meeting. Two of these experts were already Integrate Phase evaluators during the Integrate Phase of the 1st cycle: a Technology, Media, and Entertainment Executive and advisor, and a business strategist, developer, consultant, and advisor. Unlike during the first cycle, the 2nd cycle achieved gender equality by adding two women as evaluators: a project management specialist and an expert in creative business modelling. They were all suggested by Storytek

and approved by the consortium. After an introductory meeting with Storytek, they were sent the questionnaires' links on the 20th of April and handed over their evaluations on the 25th of April. To evaluate the scale-ups, they filled out a specific questionnaire, as in the Integrate Phase of the first cycle. This questionnaire was modified and improved upon feedback from the previous external experts, who were also able to compare the 2 cycles and give more extensive feedback on the program and the beneficiaries. After the evaluations, all their answers were compiled to provide a first ranking of the 12 scale-ups.

Thirdly, the scale-ups attended an online ICB meeting consisting of representatives of the 4 STADIEM hubs. Each beneficiary had a 10 min slot, divided in two: a 5 min presentation and a 5 min Q&A. The hubs representatives, unlike during the Develop Phase, did not fill out a form via Google Form, but directly on Airtable, for consistency. The form (Figure 1) consisted of 5 questions, each being answered from 1 to 5, from the lowest score to the highest/best score.

1. How well does the start-up's solution address the corporate's problem? *

Score on a scale of 1-5 (low to high)

★★★★★

2. How well are the operational and technical criteria address and planned? *

Score on a scale of 1-5 (low to high)

★★★★★

3. How well-defined and realistic are the KPIs and success criteria for the pilot? *

Score on a scale of 1-5 (low to high)

★★★★★

4. What is the potential for scalability and expansion of the start-up's solution after a successful pilot within the corporate environment? *

Score on a scale of 1-5 (low to high)

★★★★★

5. How would you rate the startup's ability to pitch their solution to potential investors / customers? *

Score on a scale of 1-5 (low to high)

FIGURE 1: SCREENSHOT OF EVALUATION QUESTIONS FROM AIRTABLE

The ranking of the start-ups was a composite of the external evaluators' ranking and the consortium meeting's ranking. Unlike during the OC1, it was decided, in concertation with the EC, to open 2 more positions for the Pilot Phase given budgetary possibilities (remaining Match OC2 third party funding budget, the fact that it would further increase the visibility of the program and that a quality evaluation procedure was followed meaning that the selected scale-ups could deliver a good Pilot Phase. All 6 selected start-ups were offered to continue in the program in the Pilot Phase and accepted the invitation to join.

- 2.3 BUDGET AND REIMBURSEMENT

Each of the 12 beneficiaries had a budget of maximum 27.500€ to spend on any activity that was deemed relevant for the Integrate Phase (travel, training, legal etc).

At the beginning of the Phase an Integrate Phase proposal was submitted with a budget for the phase. The proposed budget had to mirror the start-up's acceleration and actual needs (i.e., upskilling, integration, or piloting costs) in light of STADIEM and the Integrate Phase. The budget could be spend on:

- Engaging specialists / advisors / personnel to guarantee successful co-creation with the corporate, to manage integration and piloting etc. more effectively.
- Improving the value proposition or product/solution fit which would increase the value that is brought to the media partner.
- Hard investment in R&D.
- Developing additional capacities.
- Following workshops and training.

The beneficiary was paid 30% of its Integrate Phase budget of €27.500€ upfront at the beginning of the Integrate Phase. When a start-up's Integrate budget exceeds the maximum allowed €27.500 for this phase, the calculation will be of the maximum allowed grant (27.500€).

The remaining part was reimbursed in 2 following instalments based on actual deliverables with financial reporting and meeting KPI's midway the phase (mid-term review) and at the end of the phase (final review). For the mid-term and final review, the beneficiaries had to deliver a progress report including a financial review indicating costs and expenditures with proof and legitimations.

During the Integrate Phase, it will be possible to revise the budget in light of actual progress during the Phase, but always in collaboration with and upon approval of the mother hub.

Like during the previous phases, the beneficiaries had to inform their mother hubs about their travel and activity plans and request the approval to ensure that it was covered by STADIEM.

All expenses, described as plans in the action plan, were then filled out in the Integrate Phase budget report at the end of the Phase, in April 2023.

The payment depended on the positive assessment of the start-up's/scale-up's Integrate Phase activities. After assessment and acceptance of the progress report by the STADIEM hubs, the necessary steps for reimbursement will be taken, following VRT's rules for

reimbursement. If start-up does not meet the Phase's expectations or shows signs of negligence, reimbursement will be adjusted accordingly or cancelled altogether.

The grant of 27.500€ was, according to the Sub-Grant Agreement and the Guide for Applicants, distributed during the Integration Phase in three stages (cfr. Develop Phase): 30% of the total grant at the beginning of the phase, 35% after mid-term review and financial report and 35% after final review and financial report.

The table below shows the distribution of the budget according to the GA and Guide for Applicants OC1 and the actual distribution based on the Integrate Phase Proposal (Payment 1) and the financial reports at mid-term (Payment 2) and at final review (Payment 3). It shows that the 12 beneficiaries in total consumed **326.226 €**, hence, **99 %** of the foreseen total grant of 330.000€.

	Payment 1 30%	Payment 2 35%	Payment 3 35%	Total Period
GA	99.000€	115.500€	115.500€	330.000€
Actual 3rd Party Payment	98805€	114.214,45€	115506,73€	328.526,18€
Difference GA - Actual 3rd Party Payment	195€	1285,55€	-6,73€	1473,82€

TABLE 5: OVERVIEW OF THIRD-PARTY SUPPORT FUNDING INTEGRATE PHASE 2ND CYCLE

- 2.4 KPIS AND RESULTS

The 12 start-ups who entered the Integrate Phase met the requirements and documentation to successfully apply to the next phase and showed readiness for a public pilot. 10 decided to join the online evaluation meeting. Out of this 10, 6 (KPI is min 4) of these start-ups gathered high enough scores from the evaluation process to guarantee a qualitative piloting process and hence received an invitation to join the Pilot Phase. Interestingly, during the OC1, out of 12 participants in the Integrate Phase, 10 participated in the online evaluation meeting and 2 declined with justifications.

As the Phase is very short, unlike during the Match and Develop Phases, traveling was limited on left to the start-up's appreciation, focus was made on only one joint training activity, and mentoring was on demand from the start-up to the mother hub, upon need.

In order to achieve the main KPIs of submitting documentation and assess readiness for a public pilot via evaluation, it was decided to provide all the questionnaires and documentation shortly after the kick-off of the Phase, in February, to allow both start-ups and corporate to communicate and align as early as possible in the Phase. Only one start-up failed to have their corporate achieve this collaboration, but 11 start-ups and their corporate provided their reports either on time or slightly early. They were also able to do it in several sessions, as the Airtable questionnaires were built to remain open to modifications throughout the Phase and until the deadline.

Regarding the mandatory training event on the 28 Feb - 1- 2 March, 11 out of 12 start-ups attended 100% of the “Bootcamp”, and all of them attended the 1-to-1 meetings with both experts. Consequently, feedback from the experts regarding all the start-ups was made available to STADIEM, unlike during the OC1 event, which did not include individual meetings with designated external experts. Most start-ups were advised to focus more on their contracts with corporate, as well as the business-side of their scale-ups, as opposed to remaining too product-oriented. It helped them to incorporate it into their action plans and into their communication with their corporate. Most start-ups were in a very early stage of negotiations and admitted to needing help navigating through them, understanding what their demands could be and how to evaluate the correct worth of the solution they were providing.

Besides the mandatory event attendance and meetings upon demand with their mother hubs, STADIEM beneficiaries focused mostly on their individual activities with their corporate. Results and outcomes were described in the questionnaire that each corporate submitted by the end of the Phase.

The outcome of the Phase this time was 6 selected start-ups instead of 4.

- 2.5 DEVIATIONS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS

There were no deviations from the framework and workplan for the Integrate Phase.

- 2.6 LEARNINGS

At the end of the OC1 Integrate Phase, several axes of improvement were spotted and discussed before entering the OC2 Integrate Phase.

Timeline:

Both OC1 and OC2 Integrate Phases lasted the same: 2 months. It was once more an extremely intensive period for integration, phase management and evaluating the start-ups at the end of the phase. However, the OC2 Phase did not have the overlap that happened during the OC1, alleviating the workload and program management during the OC2. It also allowed each hub, and overall, the consortium to prepare better in terms of:

- Earlier information made available to the start-ups after the OC2 Develop Phase mid-terms, as agreed upon by the consortium after the OC1 Integrate Phase. This resulted in the 13. December first introductory meeting to the Phase.
- Continuing using the toolkit for information, issue tracking, documentation, communication with start-ups and evaluation.
- Better repartition of events, meetings, and tasks: a mandatory event earlier in the Phase, earlier planned meetings, earlier data gathering and analysis.
- Better warning of corporate communication timeline and anticipation of issues connected to their slower pace: this was the main reason behind making their questionnaire available early in the Phase and limiting the risk of issues with the deadline.
- Lessons were learned and solutions decided upon during the consortium meeting in Hamburg (November 2022) were applied.

- Corporate were also briefed in December 2022 to allow a better flow of communication.

Training:

Due to the very limited time allocated to the start-ups, start-ups were encouraged to attend as many “Training Tuesdays” as possible during the Develop Phase, to comprehend what is expected of them for the last two Phases, that arrive quite late in the program. In addition to this, the Bootcamp that was organized at the beginning of the Integrate Phase was designed upon feedback from the OC1 Integrate Phase event, in order to be more tailored to the scale-ups specific needs and challenges. It was for example noted that they seemed to need more 1-to-1 training from external experts, which was then incorporated in the OC2 event. So, in contrast to the OC1 Integrate Phase, the content of training was changed and improved: as described in D4.2, the mandatory event went from one masterclass with one expert (25th of March 2022 special CTO panel “Ask me anything” with Tallinn-based co-founder and CEO of Procurement (IT Services and IT Consulting) expert Jordan Valdma), into a 3-day Bootcamp with both an “Ask Me Anything” and 1-to-1 training.

Finances:

As explained in the D4.2, *“during the Impact assessment preparation (March - April - May 2022) and after the Integrate phase, feedback was gathered regarding the phase spendings to adapt and improve the support to the start-ups for the OC2. Modifications and adaptations are expected in the OC2.”* As a result, a more substantial budget was dedicated to training, with the introduction of the previously mentioned ‘3-day Bootcamp’, where 2 experts were mandated, compared to OC1’s one expert for one masterclass.

Evaluation process:

Two out of four external experts had given their feedback after the OC1 Integrate Phase evaluation process. Even if they had considered it “very good” overall, they also suggested improvements that were included in the OC2. Therefore:

- The questionnaire that they were submitted was lighter and the sections were revised to avoid redundancy.
- They were given the start-ups reports as early as possible.
- They had one preparatory and one feedback meetings to discuss the process, the start-ups and the program.
- The questionnaires were all from the same toolkit.

All of it resulted in a leaner, more efficient and clearer process. Finally, regarding the evaluation organization: both the tool (Airtable) and the timeline of the questionnaires were modified, for start-ups, corporate and external evaluation experts, compared to the OC1 evaluation. It proved much more convenient for STADIEM beneficiaries and external actors, but also for STADIEM hubs to track, analyse and extract data.

Toolkit

Unlike during OC1 Integrate Phase, Airtable was used from the beginning of the Phase, and for all questionnaires and reporting. It allowed consistency and improvement in analysing data (especially for the Impact Assessment D5.5 to be submitted at the end of the program).

3. PILOT PHASE

The Pilot Phase OC2 (Task T4.4) ran from May 2023 to the end of August 2023. The phase was led by MCB, with contributions from the innovation hubs NMA, STK and VRT.

Task N°	Title	Lead	Contributing Partners	Timing
4.4	Pilot	MCB	NMA, STK, VRT	M32-M36 (April – September 2023)

TABLE 6: OVERVIEW PILOT PHASE 2ND CYCLE

- 3.1 DESCRIPTION AND OBJECTIVES

During the Pilot phase the start-ups executes public pilots with the corporates in real-life environments, demonstrating their results and achievements from their STADIEM project at a large scale to a wider community of stakeholders. The pilots are evaluated for generating business value and gathering feedback from customers and other involved parties.

In the second cycle of the STADIEM program, the six top performing start-ups from the Integrate phase were invited to join and pilot their solution in the Pilot Phase, as compared to four start-ups in OC1. The consortium decided, after consulting with the Project Officer, to spend the unspent third-party funding from the Match OC2 Phase budget to increase the number of scale-ups in the Pilot Phase, without having to decrease the maximum grant per startup. In order to increase the number of accepted scale-ups, two conditions had to be fulfilled; Their results from the programme and plans for the Pilot Phase had to be of good quality above a threshold compared to the other scale-ups, and their participation in the phase had to increase the visibility and impact for the programme. Each beneficiary in the Pilot Phase can receive a maximum of € 50.000 in funding support from the STADIEM consortium during the Pilot Phase.

The Pilot Phase has a duration of four months, where the second cycle started the phase in May 2023 (M32) and concluded in August 2023 (M35). In the second cycle, the beneficiaries of the Pilot Phase were BotTalk, Druid Learning, einbliq.io, Limecraft, Scriptix, and Television.ai. Please find a short description of each of the start-ups and their project in Table 7 below.

Beneficiary	STADIEM Project	Corporate Partner(s)	Mother Hub
BotTalk	Their technology focuses on text-to-speech, allowing publishing houses with an average output of 200 news articles a day to create 8 to 30 hours of audio daily from it. Funke, NOZ, t-online, VRT, Mediafin and Roularta all partnered-up with BotTalk, leading to piloting their solution for training unique AI voices of superior quality in smaller languages like Flemish.	VRT, Mediafin, Roularta, FunkeMedia, Stroër, NOZ	VRT
Druid Learning	A white-label educational content e-commerce platform designed with inclusiveness in mind, allowing publishers to control, manage and distribute their digital content directly to their end users. They have partnered with the corporate partner of CJ Fallon Irish Educational Publisher, which is looking into improving and optimising content production through automation processes.	CJ Fallon	STK
Einbliq.io	Broadcasters and OTT companies are facing ever-growing streaming costs, mainly paid to Content Delivery Networks (CDN). With an all-embracing data analytics suite, einbliq.io, helps media companies delivering excellent and quality assured streaming services at lower cost. Working with them in this phase is RBB, on linear broadcasting and audience measurement, which will also explore streaming and energy consumption, with support from ARTE.	RBB + ARTE	NMA
Limecraft	Their cloud-based collaboration platform 'Limecraft Flow' is used by media producers worldwide to manage their workflow, allowing them to create more content faster. Built-in AI allows automation of several steps in the production process – including raw material processing, audio transcription and subtitling – finding a corporate partner in VRT, which needed to optimise their increased video production workload.	VRT	VRT

Scriptix	A full-service speech recognition provider featuring an ecosystem of (custom) speech-to-text models and additional services, aimed at enabling everybody to turn spoken word into text. Roularta Media Group is their partner in the STADIEM program, working with them on empowering transcription services with a focus on smaller language areas such as Flemish and Belgian French.	Roularta	MCB
Television.ai	AI to unlock insights from raw video footage (such as common objects, sentiments, emotions, faces, well-known people, topics, etc.) to be used for SEO, archive indexing, and even automatically create edits featuring synthetic voice over: matching with the needs of their corporate partner RBB.	RBB	MCB

TABLE 7: OVERVIEW STADIEM PROJECTS PILOT PHASE 2ND CYCLE

- 3.2 PILOT PHASE FRAMEWORK

- 3.2.1 Overview of timeline

The Pilot Phase of the second cycle started off with an onboarding meeting on 2 May with the innovation hubs and the six selected scale-ups. During this meeting, the scale-ups were presented with an overview of the Pilot Phase Framework, activities, objectives, expectations, and next steps, followed by a Q&A session. The following week, the start-ups submitted their proposal for the Pilot Phase, outlining their plans and objectives for the phase.

At the very start of the phase, the start-ups were allocated to each own mother hub. As in previous phases, the mother hubs assisted the start-up throughout the phase with coaching and follow-up and served as their main point of contact in the STADIEM consortium. The start-ups main activity in the Pilot Phase was to execute public pilots in collaboration with their corporate partner(s). They also had to demonstrate their pilot to a wider audience, including prospects similar to the corporate partner, and participate in conferences and events, meet with potential users, and disseminate the results of the project. And for those looking for funding, they also were to pitch to investors and corporates to collect interest. In late May, early June, the consortium invited all the start-ups to present and network at three industry events; Latitude59 in Estonia, MCO Mediatech Festival in Denmark, and Future Week in Norway.

Halfway through the phase, late June, the start-ups met with their mother hub for a mid-term review, closely followed by the start-ups submitting a mid-term financial report. For the final evaluation, the start-ups had to submit a final report, covering their assessment, results, and progress in the phase, as well as their spending. This report was split into two parts, part 1 covering the pilot, results, and achievements was due 18 August, and part 2, covering their costs and expenditures, was due on 4 September to cover all costs up until the official end of the phase on 30 August. Lastly as part of the evaluation, the start-ups presented their results and achievements in a final Investment Committee Meeting, alongside their corporate partners, in front of a board made up by the hubs and external experts.

To finish off the Phase and to again showcase the pilots, it was organized for the start-ups to attend IBC2023 (International Broadcasting Convention) and have the costs reimbursed by a separate financial report due straight after the convention.

Activity	Time
Onboarding Event	2 May
Submittal of Pilot Phase Proposal	10 May
Mid-term Review Meeting	26-30 June
Mid-term Financial Review Report	30 June
Evaluation Period	August
Submittal of Evaluation Report Part 1	18 August
Investment Committee Meeting	30 August
Submittal of Evaluation Report Part 2	4 September

TABLE 8: OVERVIEW PILOT PHASE 2ND CYCLE FRAMEWORK ACTIVITIES

Activity	Time
Check-ins	By appointment
Business Introductions	By appointment
Investor Meetings	By appointment

TABLE 9: OVERVIEW PILOT PHASE 2ND CYCLE PILOT-BASED NEED SUPPORT

Activity	Time
<u>Latitude59</u>	25 May (24-26 May)
<u>MCO Mediatech Festival</u>	31 May (31 May – 1 June)
<u>Future Week</u>	7 June (5 – 8 June)
<u>IBC2023</u>	15-18 September

<u>Latitude59</u>	25 May (24-26 May)
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TABLE 10: OVERVIEW PILOT PHASE 2ND CYCLE SHOWCASE AND NETWORKING ACTIVITIES

- 3.2.2 Support and Follow-up

During the Pilot Phase, each start-up/scale-up was assigned a mother hub, which throughout the phase assisted with coaching, follow-up, and served as the main point of contact for the start-up/scale-up (see table 7 for allocation). The mother hubs provided their start-ups with individual check-ins and follow up meetings based on the individual needs and wants of the start-up/scale-up, as well as in line with the framework of the phase. In addition to the check-ins, the mother hubs also facilitated business and investor introductions with companies in their networks based on the needs and requests for each start-up/scale-up.

Activity	Time	Description
Status Meetings	By appointment	Individual check-in meetings between scale-up and mother hub. Need-based.
Business Introductions	By appointment	Demand-based + cross-hub approach
Investor Meetings	By appointment	Demand-based + cross-hub approach

TABLE 11: OVERVIEW OF PILOT PHASE 2ND CYCLE NEED-BASED SUPPORT ACTIVITIES

- 3.2.3 Networking and Showcasing Activities

As one of the objectives of the Pilot Phase is for the start-ups to demonstrate their results and achievements from their STADIEM project at a large scale to a wider community of stakeholders, the STADIEM consortium organized for the start-ups to attend and showcase at five industry events in Europe. The goal of these events was to showcase the start-ups and their demos to an industry audience, to strengthen the STADIEM community, and for them to make new connections, in line with the objectives of the phase.

As the pilot Phase was active during the summer months of 2023, the industry events took place at the start of the phase, before the summer holidays were in effect. In addition, the consortium decided to organize for the start-ups to attend IBC2023 in September, after the official end of the phase, to also create impact after the summer.

- Latitude59, Tallinn, Estonia (25-26 May, 2023)

BotTalk, Wantent and Druid Learning in action on stage

The Pilot Phase showcasing events started off with a two-fold participation at Latitude59 on 25 May. Latitude59 is an annual technology and startup conference held in Estonia, bringing together innovators, entrepreneurs, investors, and thought leaders to explore and discuss the latest trends and developments in the tech and business world. Attending Latitude59 offers start-ups valuable networking opportunities, exposure to potential investors, and access to cutting-edge insights, fostering growth and collaboration within the global tech ecosystem.

The STADIEM participation at the event included a pitching session on their community stage, and a side-event, gathering over 50 participants. At the on-stage session STADIEM was presented by VRT and Druid Learning and BotTalk pitched their solutions for the audience. At the side-event, STADIEM was presented more in depth by VRT and MCB, featuring elevator pitches from BotTalk, Druid Learning, and the OC2 Integrate startup Wantent, followed by mingling with the participants.

The two Pilot start-ups attending Latitude59 reported favorable reviews of the event in a survey after attending; with an average event satisfaction score of 4.5 (all scales in the survey goes to maximum 5.0 points) and a STADIEM facilitation score of 4.0. The event was particularly noted by the start-ups for being an important startup event in the Baltics. The start-ups generated between 1-5 leads by attending the event. Their satisfaction stemmed from the quality of talks, especially those focused on legal frameworks for start-ups, and the confirmation that the Baltics are a growth market.

- **MCO Mediatech Festival, Odense, Denmark (31 May-1 June, 2023)**

einbliq.io and BotTalk on the MCO MediaTech Festival stage

On 31 May, the week after Latitude59, Einbliq.io and BotTalk showcased their pilot solutions to media corporates and investors at MCO MediaTech Festival. The annual festival is a two-day media tech conference that offers a dynamic blend of inspiration, knowledge-sharing, discussions, and networking opportunities, organised by Media City Odense. On stage, they showcase the latest advancements in communication, marketing, media production, and transformative technologies, including scale-ups from the STADIEM Pilot phase; Einbliq.io and BotTalk, and STADIEM presented by MCB.

At the MCO MediaTech Festival, the start-ups were invited to present their solution at a STADIEM pitching event on stage. They also participated in the MCO Speed Dating Event, where they got quality networking and feedback from European media corporates and investors.

The MCO Mediatech Festival 2023 received high satisfaction scores from the two start-ups in a survey after the event; averaging a 4.5 score for the event and a score of 5.0 (scale maximum is 5.0 points) for the STADIEM organization of the event participation. The two attendees were drawn to the event due to new audience engagement and lead generation in the industry.. Both participants generated between 1-5 leads and had meaningful conversations with 10-20 people during the event. Their satisfaction stemmed from various takeaways, including the event's lead generation opportunities and the opportunity for them to improve their investment pitch skills.

- **Future Week, Bergen, Norway (5-8 June, 2023)**

Television.ai on stage at Future Week

At MCB's Future Week, held in early June, the STADIEM scale-ups. Scriptix, Druid Learning, Limecraft, Television.AI, and BotTalk took center stage as they unveiled their pilot solutions to media corporates and tech enthusiasts. Now in its sixth year, the annual Future Week is a four-day festival dedicated to media tech, innovation management, news desk innovations, and future business models. Drawing in hundreds of participants from various industries, the event serves as a hub for inspiration, knowledge-sharing, discussions, and networking opportunities.

The STADIEM start-ups presented their solutions as part of the main program of the festival on 7 June, alongside presenters from known companies such as Nvidia, IBM, and the Guardian. During Future Week, the STADIEM scale-ups were not only given the opportunity to present their solutions on stage at the Media tech and trends conference, but they also actively engaged in networking events, securing valuable leads with media corporates.

In a survey, the STADIEM start-ups participating in Future Week reported that they were highly satisfied with the event, with an average event satisfaction score of 4.6 out of 5 (5.0 is the maximum score on the scale), and a score of 5.0 for STADIEM's facilitation of the event. The start-ups were drawn to the event for various reasons, ranging from specific meetings with prospects to presenting their businesses for the audience at Future Week. The start-ups generated an average of 1-5 leads by attending the event. Satisfaction of the event seemed to be largely driven by the event's focus on solving challenges in the media industry and opportunities for targeted networking.

- **IBC2023, Amsterdam, The Netherlands (15-18 September, 2023)**

Media City Bergen, NMA, Einbliq.io, Television.ai, and VRT at the EBU Booth at IBC2023.

IBC (International Broadcasting Convention) is a leading global conference for the media, entertainment, and technology sectors, highlighting the latest innovations and fostering industry connections. The event gathers a vast array of technologists, c-level managers, and companies in the media industry, to network, demo new solutions and meet existing and potential clients.

At IBC2023, on 15 September, STADIEM scale-ups, including Scriptix, Limecraft, Television.AI, and Einbliq.io, showcased their STADIEM solutions at the EBU stand in hall 10. The two-hour session, segmented into two parts, featured presentations about the programme and the startups. Additionally, the STADIEM pod at the EBU booth served as a hub for meetings for both the consortium and startups with new and existing leads.

For IBC2023, the three startups that submitted the event satisfaction survey after the event, gave the event and STADIEM's facilitation an average score of 5.0 out of 5.0. They were attracted to the event for its status in the media sector, its location, potential customer presence, and STADIEM's stand in the EBU booth. While one of the three respondents gained 1-5 leads, two others secured 15+ leads, underscoring IBC2023's vast networking potential.

Activity	Date	Description
Latitude59	25 (24-26 May)	May Pitching and matchmaking with investors. Startup and tech event.

MCO Mediatech Festival	31 (31 May – 1 June)	May	Pitching and matchmaking with investors. Media and media tech event.
Future Week	7 (5 – 8 June)	June	Pitching and networking. Media and media tech event.
IBC2023	15-18 September		<i>Showcasing event (stand exhibition is not organized by the STADIEM consortium).</i>

TABLE 12: OVERVIEW SHOWCASING AND NETWORKING EVENTS PILOT PHASE 2ND CYCLE

- 3.2.4. Upskilling and Training

With the Pilot Phase being the fourth and final phase, the STADIEM consortium decided it best to leave the STADIEM organized training sessions to the preceding phases of the program. This was also done for the Pilot Phase of the first cycle as the consortium wanted to prepare the start-ups for their pilots ahead of the pilot being live, and to let them focus on the activities of the Pilot Phase during its duration.

- 3.2.5. Evaluation Process

As with the process for the first cycle and like the preceding phases, the Pilot Phase for OC2 had a proposal, mid-term evaluation and final evaluation. Differing from the other phases, the Pilot Phase didn't have a selection process, as it was the last phase of the program for the start-ups, and no new phase for them to proceed to.

To successfully accomplish the Pilot Phase, the following requirements was to be fulfilled by each start-up/scale-up:

- Start-up/scale-up presents needs and action plan for the stage at the start of the phase (Appendix 2).
- Customer and stakeholder feedback.
- Assessment in form of market impact, collaboration, and further monetization possibilities.
- Execute a successful public pilot.
- Generate new business/investor/client leads.

The evaluation process of the Pilot Phase consisted of the following steps and procedures:

Activity	Time
Submittal of Pilot Phase Proposal	10 May

Mid-term Review Meeting	26-30 June
Mid-term Financial Review Report	30 June
Submittal of Evaluation Report Part 1	18 August
Investment Committee Meeting	30 August
Submittal of Evaluation Report Part 2	4 September

TABLE 13: OVERVIEW PILOT PHASE 2ND CYCLE EVALUATION PROCESS ACTIVITIES

Pilot Phase Proposal: The start-ups had to submit a Pilot Phase proposal (Appendix 2) at the start of the phase, outlining their plans, objectives, and budget for the phase. The details of this proposal, mainly the budget, determined the pay-out of the first instalment of the Pilot Phase. The Proposal template from OC1 was updated and tweaked according to feedback and learnings for the second cycle.

Mid-term Review: Mid-way through the phase, each startup had an individual mid-term review meeting with their assigned mother hub. During this meeting, the mother hub asked and noted down the answers to a set of pre-defined questions on the start-ups collaboration, progress, and results so far in the phase.

There was designed a Mid-term Review Protocol (Appendix 3) detailing the process of the review to ensure that each hub followed the same approach. The protocol from OC1 was updated and adjusted to fit the second cycle. The objective of the mid-term review was to map and assess the progress of each start-up. Following the mid-term review meetings, the start-ups had to submit a light financial review report (Appendix 4), to report on their expenses thus far in the phase. The combined review steps determined the pay-out of the second instalment of the phase.

Final Review: As with OC1, the goal of the final review was twofold. (1) To have a look at the progress the start-ups made during the Pilot phase and the whole STADIEM program, and to assess their results from the project. (2) To determine whether the consortium could proceed with the payment of the third and final instalment of the Pilot Phase. As part of the evaluation, each start-up had to submit a two-part report detailing (1) its progress in the Pilot Phase, its results from the program, and feedback on the program (Appendix 5), and (2) its financial review of expenditures and costs from the Pilot Phase (Appendix 6). The start-ups had to submit the second part of this report, the expense report, after the phase had ended to include all occurred costs in the phase.

As with the previous phases, the final step of the Final Review was an Investment Committee Meeting where the start-ups presented their project and achieved results in the pilot phase and in the project in total, while their Corporate Partner presented their assessment and achieved value from the project. The Investment Committee meeting was a meeting with the four innovation hubs of STADIEM (VRT, STK, NMA & MCB), the six selected scale-ups in the Pilot Phase (BotTalk, Druid Learning, einbliq.io, Limecraft, Scriptix, and Television.ai), their corporate partners (NOZ, CJ Fallon, RBB, VRT, and Roularta, and external Investment Committee members. As BotTalk's project included several Corporate Partners, the consortium decided that they only had to bring one Corporate Partner to the ICM to represent

their collaborators. The external Investment Committee members of this ICM, were three external experts who had been involved in previous selection processes earlier in the program.

Each scaleup was provided with a timeslot of 25 minutes for the ICM. As the Pilot Phase marks the end of these start-ups' participation in the STADIEM program and there is no following phase, the Investment Committee members did not score the pitches. The Investment Committee's role was to ask any questions they might have and provide feedback on the start-ups' journey and results.

After the evaluation and phase had ended, each start-up received a letter of recommendation signed by each partner of the consortium.

- 3.3 BUDGET AND REIMBURSEMENT

The maximum financial contribution for the Pilot Phase is €50.000 per start-up, by accepting 6 start-ups into the OC2 Pilot Phase, this amounts to a total budget of €300.000 in third party funding in the Pilot phase of this cycle. As stated in the Sub-Grant Agreement, 30% of the requested contribution was paid to the start-ups upon approved budget after being selected in the Pilot phase, with them also having to submit their updated Sub-Grant Agreement with a wet-ink signature. The start-ups budget submitted in their Pilot Phase Proposal formed the basis of calculating their instalments in the phase. Should a start-up's Pilot phase budget (requested contribution) exceed the maximum allowed financial contribution of € 50.000 for this phase, the calculation will be 30% of the maximum allowed € 50.000.

The remaining 70% of the requested contribution are reimbursed in two instalments after successful delivery of the KPI's and objectives defined in the Pilot phase plan (Appendix 2). This means that the reimbursements of the remaining contribution will be based on actual deliverables, mid-way through the Pilot phase and at the end of the Pilot phase. For the Mid-term review (Appendix 3 and Appendix 4) and the final evaluation report (Appendix 5 and Appendix 6), the start-ups had to deliver a report of their financial review, indicating costs and expenditures. All reports were to be approved by the start-ups designated mother hub in order to proceed with the payments.

The payment depends on the positive assessment of the start-up's Pilot phase activities. The budget should always mirror the start-up's acceleration and upskilling in light of the STADIEM objectives. It may be spent on e.g.,

- Dissemination and promotion activities and materials
- Travel and accommodation expenses related to the main activities in the Pilot Phase
- Tickets to attend conferences and events in line with the objectives of the Pilot Phase
- To develop additional capacities
- To follow workshops and training relevant to the phase

After assessment and acceptance of the final evaluation report by the STADIEM hubs, the necessary steps for reimbursement will be taken, following VRT's rules for reimbursement. If a start-up does not meet the Phase's expectations or shows signs of negligence, reimbursement will be adjusted accordingly or cancelled altogether.

All 6 start-ups in the Pilot Phase of OC2 were determined eligible for their three instalments of the Pilot Phase.

The large trade event of IBC2023 was to be organized after the Pilot Phase OC2 had officially ended, on 15-18 September. Costs in relation to this event could not be included in the end-of-phase report, or any previous reports, as they had not yet been incurred. Due to the expressed wishes of the start-ups to attend this event, and with the objectives of attending this event was in line with the Pilot Phase objectives, the consortium decided to open for a separate IBC2023 cost reporting after the event had occurred (Appendix 7). The demand to attend this event was already expressed by several start-ups at the Pilot Phase information meeting that had been held in December 2022, outlining the framework of the phase, which gave the consortium ample time to find a solution in order to include these costs for the start-ups.

Including the costs for IBC2023 in the Pilot Phase budget was decided in order for this relevant Pilot Phase activity to be supported by the STADIEM grant for the start-ups as an extension to the phase. The Pilot Phase of OC2 had been active during the summer months, which is known for low activity when it comes to larger industry events. By allowing for IBC costs to be reimbursed, the start-ups had the opportunity to attend a large industry event (i.e. IBC2023) to create impact with dissemination not only at the very start of the phase, but also after the summer holidays. Four start-ups took advantage of this opportunity and attended IBC. The reimbursements were to be a part of their maximum grant for the phase and their preliminary budget, and were not to be paid as an addition to the maximum €50.000 each. Only one startup submitted a separate IBC2023 cost reporting form as they were the only one of the four startups at the event who hadn't already reached their maximum grant in the previous reporting period.

The table below shows the distribution of the budget according to the GA and Guide for Applicants OC2 and the actual distribution based on the Pilot Phase Proposal (Payment 1) and the financial reports at mid-term (Payment 2) and final review (Payment 3). It shows that the 6 beneficiaries in total consumed 300.00 euro of the foreseen total grant of 300.000 euro.

	Payment 1 30%	Payment 2 35%	Payment 3 35%	Total Period
GA + Guide for Applicants	90.000€	105.000€	105.000€	300.000€
Actual 3rd Party Payment	89.535€	104.457,5€	106.007,5 €	300.000€
Difference GA - Actual 3rd Party Payment	465€	542,5€	- 1007,5 €	0€

TABLE 14: OVERVIEW PILOT PHASE 2ND CYCLE THIRD PARTY FUNDING BUDGET AND PAYMENT

- 3.4 KPI'S AND RESULTS

The main KPI of the Pilot Phase was the selection of at least 4 start-ups/scale-ups to start the Phase. As mentioned above, due to the remaining Third Party-funding budget from several start-ups not utilizing the maximum grant in the Match Phase, STADIEM were able to accept six start-ups into the OC2 Pilot Phase. The six top-performing start-ups from the Integrate Phase (BotTalk, Druid Learning, einbliq.io, Limecraft, Scriptix, and Television.ai) were invited to and accepted the invitation to the Pilot Phase. All six start-ups completed the phase, and met the expectations of the phase, leaving four successfully executed public pilots.

One of the main objectives of the phase was for the start-ups to disseminate and showcase their pilots, generating interest from relevant stakeholders. As visualized in the graph below, the start-ups made an average of 18 business leads, 8 investor leads, and 63 client leads in the pilot phase up until mid-august. The leads were reported by the start-ups themselves in the End-of-phase Report, and exclude the leads made at IBC2023 as that event took place after the reporting deadline. The business leads represent potential new partners, re-sellers, or other types of strategic relationships that could help expand the scale-ups reach and capabilities. The investor leads refers to potential investors who have shown interest in financially backing the scale-up. The client leads are potential new customers who could directly contribute to the scale-up's revenue, validating its business model and market fit.

GRAPH 1: AVERAGE NUMBER OF LEADS GENERATED IN THE PILOT PHASE 2ND CYCLE

Graph 2 below shows the number of leads per scale-up. From this table, one can see that there are some great variations in the number of leads per startup, per category. The lead generation will naturally vary per scale-up as each scale-up has different solutions, maturity and focuses. For instance, scale-ups looking for funding will work harder to generate investor leads, than scale-ups that are not currently looking to raise funds. Also, it is important to note that these leads were the ones the scale-ups self-reported to have generated in the first three

months of the Pilot Phase alone, not the entire duration of the program, and one can see that all scale-ups generated leads in one form or another.

GRAPH 2: NUMBER OF LEADS GENERATED BY SCALE-UP IN THE PILOT PHASE 2ND CYCLE

- 3.5 DEVIATIONS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS

No deviations of gravitas had to be made during the Pilot Phase of the second cycle.

- 3.6 LEARNINGS

Overall, the different activities of the framework of the pilot phase worked well in practice as planned. At the end of the phase, the six scale-ups were asked to provide feedback on the phase and their experience in the programme overall:

Findings from the survey at the end of the Pilot Phase tells us that the STADIEM programme has been received largely positively by the scale-ups in the Pilot Phase, offering valuable exposure, networking opportunities, and financial support. The program's iterative approach was commended for its flexibility, which is crucial for start-ups and scale-ups. Most of the scale-ups found value in the networking opportunities, the chance to pilot with corporates, and the funding. However, there were recurring areas for improvement: the Match phase was often cited as being too short, and the reporting requirements were sometimes seen as inefficient and repetitive. Some scale-ups suggested a more streamlined approach to reporting and better clarity on objectives and planning. The program's exposure opportunities, particularly at events

like IBC, were appreciated. Overall, despite some areas of feedback, the scale-ups expressed gratitude for STADIEM's support in advancing innovation and collaboration in the European media landscape.

The reporting in the Pilot Phase and overall, in OC2 was iterated and made more streamlined than in OC1 based on the feedback from the scale-ups in OC1. Still, the feedback from the Pilot Phase scale-ups in OC2 shows that there is still room for improvement when it comes to the reporting in the programme.

As with the Pilot Phase of OC1, the timing of the Pilot Phase of OC2 was less than ideal, falling in the middle of the summer holiday. To mitigate this inconvenience, the consortium decided to organize several showcasing events for the scale-ups in the Pilot Phase at the start of the phase, and to add the IBC2023 event after the official end of the Pilot Phase. This facilitated the scale-ups objectives to showcase their solution throughout the phase, and the different events were well welcomed by the scale-ups. Of course, having scale-ups in different areas of the industry, not all events will be as relevant for them all, but with a good mix of STADIEM organized events in the OC2 Pilot Phase, all scale-ups attended at least two events in this cycle, which is an improvement from the first Pilot Phase.

4. CONCLUSION

This report has provided a detailed overview of the activities of the Integration and Pilot Phases of the second cycle of the STADIEM Innovation Program that took place from February to September 2023. We present below the main outcomes and results for the two phases, the key info on budget and grant distribution and the key operational actions to retain. This is followed by a look at the major insights and lessons learned and ends with a more global view on the 2 cycles of the Innovation Program.

Outcomes and Results

On the level of KPI's for both phases, STADIEM managed to achieve the set targets.

At least 12 beneficiaries from the Develop Phase of the second cycle were selected to the Integrate Phase and they could integrate technically and/or service level their solution with the corporate in order to be ready for a public pilot. This is demonstrated by the submission of the final review reports at the end of the phase as well as participation in the remote expert evaluation taking place in the final review process. Only two of the 12 beneficiaries declined a selection for the Pilot Phase shortly before the pilot selection meeting of the ICB. In the case of the scale-up which announced they were dropping out of the program entirely, miscommunication from the corporate, added to a bad timing management regarding the report, was perceived.

For the OC2 Pilot phase, the STADIEM project managed to select 6 beneficiaries from the 10 beneficiaries that declared to candidate for the Pilot Phase and at least 6 of them have set up public pilot executions. Thanks to these pilots, the six beneficiaries managed to acquire an average of 18 business leads, 8 investor leads, and 63 client leads in the pilot phase up until mid-august. They participated at the STADIEM-organized demo-events at Future Week, MCO Mediatech Festival, IBC, and Latitude59 allowing customers to discover and experiment with the solutions. The overall success stories presented show that STADIEM as a program has had a highly beneficial impact for the European start-up/scale-up innovation ecosystem.

Budget and grant distribution

On a budget and grant distribution level, we see that for both cycles the foreseen budget was almost consumed totally (99% in the case of Integration; 100% in the case of Piloting).

Running the program

Training in the Integration Phase was organized at the beginning, in order to let the beneficiaries be fully aware of the importance of the activities, while in the Pilot Phase, STADIEM organized to participate in four industry events to showcase the demos of the 6 final beneficiaries. Besides these STADIEM events, the 6 pilot start-ups took their own initiatives with their allocated grant to showcase the solution at relevant venues in Europe, but also beyond (SXSW, Event Tech Live Las Vegas...).

Learnings and future perspective

The STADIEM Innovation Program generated very qualitative results both in terms of outcomes, budget and grant distribution, and in terms of program management. Moreover, the lessons learned from the OC1 significantly improved both areas of results. The previous report was used as a base to raise the quality and efficiency of the whole program, with very satisfactory results.

The OC2 Integrate phase had several opportunities for improvement in four categories: timeline, training, finances, and evaluation of the start-ups. The Integrate phase was very short, leading to an intensive period for the start-ups, hubs, and consortium. The start-ups had limited time for training, and deviations in spending were expected in the next phase during OC1, not during OC2. Feedback from external experts helped improve the evaluation process and reporting procedures for a more efficient process in this cycle, which proved very valuable.

The OC2 Pilot Phase worked well overall, with learnings taken from the OC1, also related to presenting the Phase early (at the same time as the Integrate Phase in December 2022 and making reporting accessible early in the Phase to give flexibility to the program). The timing of the Pilot Phase, spanning over the summer holidays was again less than ideal to plan and organize events to showcase the start-ups' products and was challenging. It was also a challenge for start-ups to keep good communication with corporate in a period of holiday, when relevant stakeholders are not in office and delay their responses and reactivity is low.

Incorporating the lessons and learnings from OC1 was very successful and helped the program be more tailored to the start-ups and their corporate, as well as less demanding on the consortium in terms of program management.

STADIEM Innovation Program: overall assessment

On an operational level, we see that the project managed to organize two qualitative full cycles. The program's framework had a very intense rhythm in both phases, which allows it to keep a consistent pace in the innovation track, as well as enable the start-ups to actively engage their corporate along the process. Mother hubs provided crucial support and mentoring based on individual / specific needs from the beneficiaries and facilitated leads through their own networks and expertise.

Besides the two exits, the overall result of STADIEM's OC2, is that for each of the 4 phases, KPI's of minimum participation at the beginning of the phase and minimum selection at the end of the phase were consistently met. During the trajectory of the OC1 and OC2, there was never a breach in cooperation between a corporate. No start-up ended the cooperation prematurely or unexpectedly either.

APPENDIX 1 – PILOT PHASE FRAMEWORK

PILOT PHASE

May 2023 – August 2023

Grant Agreement No.: 957321
Call: H2020-ICT-2018-2020
Topic: ICT-44-2020
Type of action: IA

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1. OVERALL EXPECTATIONS

1.1 ACTIVITIES

Startups will execute public pilots with the corporate in real-life environments. The pilots are evaluated for generating business value and gathering feedback from customers and other involved parties. The final pilots are assessed in terms of market impact, collaboration, and further monetization possibilities.

The aim of the pilot phase is for the scale-ups and their corporate partners to execute public pilots, demonstrating their results and achievements from their STADIEM project at a large scale to a wider community. This entails that the scale-up must disseminate and demo the pilot publicly. The public pilots can be either client or external consumer focused and must be visible for the public over the course of several months.

Every activity during the pilot phase aims to engage new customers, corporates, partners, end-users, investors, and other stakeholders. The main activities in the pilot phase are to:

- *Expand: Demonstrate pilot to a wider audience, including prospects similar to the corporate partner.*
- *Promote: Participate in conferences and events, meet with potential users, and disseminate the results of the project.*
- *Invest: Pitch to investors and corporates, collect interest.*

1.2 EXPECTED RESULTS

Guide for Applicants, p. 22/23:

Expected results

To successfully accomplish the Pilot Phase, the following requirements should be fulfilled by each start-up/scale-up:

- *Start-up/scale-up presents needs and action plan for the stage at the start of the phase*
- *Customer and stakeholder feedback*
- *Assessment in form of market impact, collaboration and further monetization possibilities*
- *Execute a successful public pilot*
- *Generate new business/investor/client leads*

The evaluation of this Phase will follow two intertwined steps: 1) submittal of a final evaluation report, to be reviewed by the STADIEM Hubs, and 2) a pitching session for the STADIEM Investment Committee, consisting of at least 3 external experts and 1 representative per STADIEM hub. Formal approval by the Investment Committee, unlocks last financing.

Additionally, a mid-term review will take place halfway through the Phase, to check the Start-Up/Scale-Ups' progress in relation to the original needs, objectives and action plan, that resulted in their selection for the Pilot Phase.

2. EVALUATION REPORT

At the end of the Pilot Phase, the scale-ups will have to submit an evaluation report, including:

- Summary of Objectives and Ambitions
- Summary of Pathway to Impact
- Summary of Implementation
- Corporate Assessment
- STADIEM Journey

See evaluation report in [Airtable](#) (individual links to be distributed).

3. BUDGET AND REIMBURSEMENT

3.1 BUDGET

The Budget should always mirror the scale-up's acceleration + skilling/upskilling in light of STADIEM objectives.

Tips and tricks to spend the budget:

- Dissemination and promotion activities and materials
- Travel and accommodation expenses related to the main activities in the Pilot Phase
- Tickets to attend conferences and events in line with the objectives of the Pilot Phase
- To develop additional capacities
- To follow workshops and training relevant to the phase

3.2 REIMBURSEMENT

The maximum financial contribution for the Pilot Phase is €50.000 per startup, the payment will depend on a positive assessment of the startup's Pilot Phase activities.

Startups will be paid 30% of the requested contribution upon approved budget after being selected in the Pilot Phase. When a startup's Pilot Phase budget (requested contribution) exceeds the maximum allowed financial contribution of € 50.000 for this phase, the calculation will be 30% of the maximum allowed € 50.000.

The remaining 70% of the requested contribution will be reimbursed in two installments after successful delivery of the KPI's and objectives defined in the Pilot Phase plan. This means that the reimbursements of the remaining contribution will be based on actual deliverables, mid-way through the Pilot Phase and at the end of the Pilot Phase. For the Mid-term Review and the final Evaluation Report, the startups must deliver a report of their financial review, indicating costs and expenditures.

After assessment and acceptance of the final evaluation report by the STADIEM hubs, the necessary steps for reimbursement will be taken, following VRT's rules for reimbursement.

If a scale-up does not meet the Phase's expectations or shows signs of negligence, reimbursement will be adjusted accordingly or canceled altogether.

1 TIMELINE: PILOT FRAMEWORK

Activity	Time	Description
Onboarding Event	2 May	<p>One joint meeting with the innovation hubs and the four selected scale-ups.</p> <p>During this meeting, the scale-ups will get an overview of the Pilot Phase Framework, activities, objectives, expectations, and next steps, followed by a Q&A session.</p>
Submittal of Pilot Phase Proposal	10 May	<p>The scale-ups will have to submit a Pilot Phase Proposal outlining their plans and objectives for the Pilot Phase.</p> <p>The Airtable form will be distributed after acceptance into the Pilot Phase.</p> <p>The Pilot Phase Proposal determines the payout of the first installment of the Pilot Phase financial contribution.</p>
Mid-term Review Meeting	26-30 June	<p>Individual meetings between motherhubs and the scale-ups.</p> <p>Each scale-up details their progress of the first half of the Pilot Phase.</p>
Mid-term Financial Review Report	30 June	<p>Each scale-up submits their financial review of expenditures and costs from the Pilot Phase this far.</p> <p>The mid-term review determines the payout of the second installment of the Pilot Phase financial contribution.</p>
Evaluation Period	August	<p>Scale-ups perform a final evaluation and assessment in terms of market impact, collaboration with corporate partner(s), and further monetization possibilities of the scale-ups projects.</p>

Activity	Time	Description
Submittal of Evaluation Report Part 1	18 August	<p>The report will be distributed on Airtable. The report covers the scale-ups collaboration, pilot, results, assessment, and achievement in the Pilot Phase.</p> <p>The evaluation report determines the payout of the third installment of the Pilot Phase financial contribution.</p>
Investment Committee Meeting	30 August	<p>One joint meeting with the four innovation hubs, the four selected scale-ups, their corporate partners, and Investment Committee members. Scale-up presents their project and achieved results in the pilot phase and in the project in total. The corporate partner presents their assessment and achieved value from the project.</p>
Submittal of Evaluation Report Part 2	4 September	<p>Each scale-up submits their financial review of expenditures and costs from the Pilot Phase this far.</p> <p>The evaluation report determines the payout of the third installment of the Pilot Phase financial contribution.</p> <p>Note that all questions in the Evaluation Report need to be answered within this deadline to ensure the payout of the third instalment of the Pilot Phase. Any missing responses may lead to a deduction from the final instalment.</p>

2 TIMELINE: NEED-BASED SUPPORT

Activity	Time	Description
Status Meetings	By appointment	Individual check-in meetings between scale-up and mother hub. Need-based.
Business Introductions	By appointment	Demand-based + cross-hub approach
Investor Meetings	By appointment	Demand-based + cross-hub approach

3 TIMELINE: NETWORKING AND SHOWCASING EVENTS

Activity	Date	Location	Description
<u>Latitude59</u>	25 May (24-26 May)	Tallinn, Estonia	Pitching and matchmaking with investors. Startup and tech event. More details to follow.
<u>MCO Mediatech Festival</u>	May 31 – June 1	Odense, Denmark	Pitching and matchmaking with investors. Media and media tech event. More details to follow.
<u>Future Week</u>	7 June (5 – 8 June)	Bergen, Norway	Pitching and networking. Media and media tech event. More details to follow.
<u>IBC2023</u>	15-18 September	Amsterdam, The Netherlands	<i>Showcasing event (stand exhibition is not organized by the STADIEM consortium).</i> More details to follow.

4 COMMUNICATION GUIDELINES

The announcement of the scale-ups that have been selected for the Pilot Phase is under embargo until the STADIEM consortium publishes the results on their website.

Keep in mind that all communication activities about the project should correctly refer to STADIEM as a European project accepted under the Horizon 2020 framework programme. All communication should mention the following, together with the project name.

If you attend any events outside of the Pilot Phase Framework:

- Make sure to inform your designated motherhub about your attendance
- Send your motherhub a photo of your presentation/representation at the event, where the STADIEM logo should be clearly visible. This should also be included when declaring your expenditures and costs for the phase.

Grant Agreement No.: 957321
Call: H2020-ICT-2018-2020
Topic: ICT-44-2020
Type of action: IA

APPENDIX 2 – PROPOSAL INTEGRATE TO PILOT

Submit Integrate to Pilot Proposal

Deadline 8 May at 23:59 CEST.

Startup name

Your name

Summary of your work

Provide a short summary of your work, activities, and main achievements in the Pilot Phase. Compared to your project plan submitted at the start of the phase. Explain any deviations.

Upload budget

Upload your budget this far, showing your planned and current costs (see provided budget reporting template).

📄 Drop files here

Summary of your progress

Give a short description of your progress this far on reaching your KPIs, Deliverables, Milestones, and other planned activities. Compared to your project plan submitted at the start of the phase. Explain any deviations.

Risks and challenges

List the risks and challenges you have encountered this far in the phase and how you handled/mitigated them.

Personnel costs

State your personnel costs that have occurred up to this point in the Pilot Phase (in Euros).

Equipment costs

State your equipment costs that have occurred up to this point in the Pilot Phase (in Euros).

Consumables costs

State your consumables costs that have occurred up to this point in the Pilot Phase (in Euros).

Training costs

State your training costs that have occurred up to this point in the Pilot Phase (in Euros).

Travel costs

State your travel costs that have occurred up to this point in the Pilot Phase (in Euros).

Subcontracting costs

State your subcontracting costs that have occurred up to this point in the Pilot Phase (in Euros).

Budget explanation

Explain how the budget has been spent this far. Explain any deviations between planned and actual costs.

Upload proof of costs

Upload your financial proof of costs (Invoices etc.).

📄 Drop files here

Comment (optional)

Is there something you would like to add about your participation and experience in the Pilot Phase this far?

Submit

Never submit passwords through this form. [Report malicious form](#)

Budget Pilot Phase						
All costs should be listed in Euros.						
	M1 - May Budget	M2 - June Budget	M3 - July Budget	M4 - August Budget	M5 - September Budget (only IBC costs are eligible)	Total
Personnel costs						
Equipment						
Consumables						
Training						
Travel						
Subcontracting						
Total in EUR	0	0	0	0	0	0

APPENDIX 3 – PILOT PHASE 2ND CYCLE MID-TERM REVIEW PROTOCOL

MID-TERM REVIEW PROTOCOL - PILOT PHASE OC2

This protocol aims to ensure that all four hubs share the same approach for the mid-term review with the scale-up allocated to their mother hub. After the mid-term review, the hubs should be familiar with the progress of their scale-up and be able to decide if the second instalment for their scale-up should be paid in full, partially, or not at all, based on their progress in the phase.

Timeline

- 22 June: MCB will communicate the questions in the protocol and the links for the mid-term financial review to the scale-ups in the Pilot Phase
- 26-30 June: Mid-term review meetings (approx. 30-45 minutes) between the mother hubs and their scale-up. The hubs follow the questions in this protocol (see the next pages) and make notes of the scale-ups answers.
- 30 June, 23:59 CEST: Deadline for the submission of the mid-term financial review, submission in Airtable.

Mid-term review meeting

The goal of the mid-term review meeting is to challenge the scale-ups on their progress vis-à-vis the project plan they submitted at the start of the Pilot phase and to provide advice/coach them where needed. Each hub will have to schedule a meeting with the scale-up with them as their mother hub (26-30 June 2023):

- MCB - Scriptix & Television.ai
- NMA - Einbliq.io
- VRT - BotTalk & Limecraft
- STK - Druid Learning

List of questions to be asked during the mid-term review meeting

Objectives and ambition	<p>How is your current progress aligned with the project plan, in terms of:</p> <p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How are you on track in meeting the set objectives? All the objectives are met <p>Methodology:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How does your (agile) approach work? • Did you have to pivot? If so, how? • Where do you stand vis-à-vis the assumptions you made at the start of the phase? • What challenges have you encountered and how have you dealt with them?
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What risks have you encountered and how have you dealt with them?
<p>Pathway to impact</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How is your current growth in line with your expectations in the project plan for the phase? • Is your corporate partner committed to the use case? • What does the collaboration with the corporate partner look like (e.g. co-creation workshops, meetings, steerco,...)? • What impact have you generated for your scale-up during the past months? Are you on track? • What impact have you generated for your corporate partner during the past months? Are you on track? • How many business leads have you generated in the Pilot Phase? How many of these are a result of your STADIEM project/activities? • How many investor leads have you generated in the Pilot Phase? How many of these are a result of your STADIEM project/activities? • How many new clients have you recruited in the Pilot Phase? How many of these are a result of your STADIEM project/activities?
<p>Implementation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How is your progress this far in the phase compared to your project plan in terms of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Timeline: prediction versus actual? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ If any deviations: please elaborate why and actions taken. ○ Budget: prediction versus actual? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ If any deviations: please elaborate why and actions taken. ○ Deliverables: prediction versus actual? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ If any deviations: please elaborate why and actions taken. • What is your progress on the KPIs you set in the project plan? • What communication activities have you set up about your pilot? (Posts, events, showcases, pitches, expos, videos, etc.) • What was the target group of your communication? • What impact has these communication activities had for your company?

Mid-term review report

For the mid-term financial report, the start-ups will need to fill in their answers in their individual Airtable link; here, they can also go back and edit their answers up until the deadline: 30 June, 23:59 CEST. The links will be distributed by MCB.

APPENDIX 4 – MID-TERM FINANCIAL REVIEW REPORT PILOT PHASE

Mid-term Financial Review Report Pilot Phase

Deadline: 22 July, 2022, 23:59 CEST.

You are required to fill in all fields in this questionnaire as part of your Mid-term Financial Review Report.

Startup name

Your name

Summary of your work

Provide a short summary of your work, activities, and main achievements in the Pilot Phase. Compared to your project plan submitted at the start of the phase. Explain any deviations.

Summary of your progress

Give a short description of your progress this far on reaching your KPIs, Deliverables, Milestones, and other planned activities. Compared to your project plan submitted at the start of the phase. Explain any deviations.

Risks and challenges

List the risks and challenges you have encountered this far in the phase and how you handled/mitigated them.

Personnel costs

State your personnel costs that have occurred up to this point in the Pilot Phase (in Euros).

Equipment costs

State your equipment costs that have occurred up to this point in the Pilot Phase (in Euros).

Consumables costs

State your consumables costs that have occurred up to this point in the Pilot Phase (in Euros).

Training costs

State your training costs that have occurred up to this point in the Pilot Phase (in Euros).

Travel costs

State your travel costs that have occurred up to this point in the Pilot Phase (in Euros).

Subcontracting costs

State your subcontracting costs that have occurred up to this point in the Pilot Phase (in Euros).

Budget explanation

Explain how the budget has been spent this far. Explain any deviations between planned and actual costs.

Upload budget

Upload your budget this far, showing your planned and current costs (see provided budget reporting template)

provided budget reporting template).

⬇ Drop files here

Upload proof of costs

Upload your financial proof of costs (Invoices etc.).

⬇ Drop files here

Comment (optional)

Is there something you would like to add about your participation and experience in the Pilot Phase this far?

Submit

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Cost Reporting Mid-term Financial Review Pilot Phase								
All costs should be reported in Euros.								
	M1		M2		Total		Deviations	
	Budget	Actual costs	Budget	Actual costs	Budget	Actual costs		
Personnel costs								0
Equipment								0
Consumables								0
Training								0
Travel								0
Subcontracting								0
Total in EUR	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

APPENDIX 5 – PILOT END-OF-PHASE EVALUATION REPORT

Pilot End-of-phase Evaluation Report Part

1

Deadline: 18 August (23:59 CET).

You are required to fill in all fields of this questionnaire by 18 August.

Note that all questions in the Evaluation Report need to be answered within the deadline to ensure the payout of the third instalment of the Pilot Phase.

Please give answers specific to the phase, the whole programme, or both, depending on the field description.

1. Startup Name

2. Your Name

3. Number of Employees in the Start-up

SUMMARY OF OBJECTIVES AND AMBITIONS

4. Summary of Work and Activities

Give a summary of the work and activities performed during the Pilot phase. How did you do compared to your submitted action plan and objectives? (Phase specific)

5. Main Results and Achievements

Give a summary of the main results achieved throughout the Pilot Phase and main achievements in the programme. How did you do compared to your objectives?
(Phase specific and throughout the whole programme)

6. Innovation Capacity

Describe in short, your achieved innovation capacity throughout the programme, a prognosis on how the project has impacted your future innovation capacity, as well as the achieved innovation capacity for your

innovation capacity, as well as the achieved innovation capacity for your corporate partner.
(Phase specific and throughout the whole programme)

7. Impact for Start-up

Summary of the impact the Pilot Phase has had for the startup. Include the most important highlights from the whole programme.
(Phase specific and throughout the whole programme)

8. Impact for Corporate Partner

Summary of the impact the Pilot Phase has had for the corporate. Include the most important highlights from the whole programme.
(Phase specific and throughout the whole programme)

9. Collaboration

Describe the nature of the collaboration with the corporate, and assess how the collaboration has worked. What went well? What could be improved? Important lessons learned?
(Phase specific and throughout the whole programme)

10. Customer and Stakeholder Feedback

Describe the customer and stakeholder feedback you have collected for the solution(s) you have developed during the STADIEM programme.

11. Assessment

Provide an assessment in form of market impact, collaboration and further monetization possibilities for the solution/product you have developed through the STADIEM programme.

12. Business Leads

How many business leads (potential new partners, re-sellers, etc.) have you generated in the Pilot Phase?

13. Investor Leads

How many investor leads have you generated in the Pilot Phase?

14. Client Leads

How many client leads (potential new customers) have you generated in the Pilot Phase?

15. Customer Acquisition Cost

What is the Customer Acquisition Cost (in euros) of the solution you developed in the STADIEM programme?

SUMMARY OF IMPLEMENTATION

16. Timeline and Work Plan

Compare your actual timeline with your initial timeline. Explain any deviations. (Phase specific)

17. Deliverables, Milestones, and KPI's

Have you reached the deliverables, milestones, and KPI's as planned in your proposal? Make sure to explain actual progress and any deviations. (Phase specific)

18. Personnel Efforts

Compare your actual personnel efforts with planned personnel efforts. Explain any deviations. (Phase specific)

19. Risks and Mitigation

Describe any risks you encountered during the Pilot Phase and how you mitigated them. Did you have to pivot? Did you encounter any risks you didn't foresee? (Phase specific)

20. Training

Give an overview of the training, workshops, courses, etc. that you have completed in the Pilot Phase. (Phase specific)

Were the training and support offered enough? Should there be more or less? And if yes then what topics? (Throughout the whole programme)

21. Communication and Dissemination

Describe your communication, dissemination, and outreach activities in the Pilot Phase (marketing campaign, event attendance, expos, pitching, etc.). What impact did these activities have for your start-up? (Phase specific)

ASSESSMENT

22. STADIEM Journey

This is your opportunity to provide your assessment of the STADIEM programme as a participant. Please see the questions below as a guide on what to include in this part of the report.

How were your experiences throughout the programme and during each phase?

What have you achieved of value from participating and getting this far in the STADIEM programme?

What feedback do you want to provide to the STADIEM consortium?

How could your experience in the programme have been improved?

What were the things that weren't great?

Which parts of the programme provided you with the most value?

How will you describe your involvement in the programme?

What could you have done differently to benefit more from your participation in the programme?

What are the most critical changes that STADIEM should implement?

(Throughout the whole programme)

23. Corporate Assessment

Submit a statement from your corporate partner(s) highlighting their involvement in the activities in the Pilot phase and how the project has created value for them.

📄 Drop files here

Parent Record ID *

IMPORTANT - do not change this record! Let it stay as is, this ID is unique for your company.

Submit

APPENDIX 6 – PILOT END-OF-PHASE EVALUATION REPORT PART 2

Pilot End-of-phase Evaluation Report Part 2

Part 2 of the Pilot End-of-phase Evaluation Report pertains to the budget and costs of the Pilot Phase.

This part of the report, part 2, is to be completed by 4 September (23:59 CET) to include all occurred costs in the Pilot Phase.

Note that you are required to fill in all fields of this questionnaire within the deadline to ensure the payout of the third installment of the Pilot Phase. Any missing responses by 4 September (23:59 CET) may lead to a deduction from the final installment.

1. Startup Name

2. Your Name

FINANCIAL REPORTING

3. Personnel Costs

State your total personnel costs that have occurred in the Pilot Phase (in Euros).

4. Equipment Costs

State your total equipment costs that have occurred in the Pilot Phase (in Euros).

5. Consumables Costs

State your total consumables costs that have occurred in the Pilot Phase (in Euros).

6. Training Costs

State your total training costs that have occurred in the Pilot Phase (in Euros).

7. Travel Costs

State your total travel costs that have occurred in the Pilot Phase (in Euros).

8. Subcontracting Costs

State your total subcontracting costs that have occurred in the Pilot Phase (in Euros).

9. Budget Explanation

Explain how the budget has been spent this far. Explain any deviations between planned and actual costs. Include an explanation of how the budget was spent. Justify subcontracting if there is any. Give an indication of in-kind contributions from the scale-up and the corporate if applicable.

10. Upload Budget

Upload your budget this far, showing your planned and current costs (see provided budget reporting template).

 Drop files here

11. Upload Proof of Costs

Upload your financial proof of costs (Invoices etc.). Please see provided zip file.

 Drop files here

Step 1/3: Home

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Cost Reporting End-of-phase Financial Review Pilot Phase

All costs should be reported in Euros.

	M3		M4		Total		Deviations
	Budget	Actual costs	Budget	Actual costs	Budget	Actual costs	
Personnel costs							0
Equipment							0
Consumables							0
Training							0
Travel							0
Subcontracting							0
Total in EUR	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

APPENDIX 7 – IBC2023 REIMBURSEMENT FORM

IBC2023 Reimbursement Form

1. Startup Name

2. Your Name

FINANCIAL REPORTING

3. Personnel Costs

State your total personnel costs at IBC2023 (in Euros)

State your total personnel costs at IBC2023 (in Euros).

4. Equipment Costs

State your total equipment costs at IBC2023 (in Euros).

5. Consumables Costs

State your total consumables costs at IBC2023 (in Euros).

6. Training Costs

State your total training costs at IBC2023 (in Euros).

7. Travel Costs

State your total travel costs at IBC2023 (in Euros).

8. Subcontracting Costs

State your total subcontracting costs at IBC2023 (in Euros).

9. Budget Explanation

10. Upload Budget

Upload your budget, following the same template as with previous financial reporting.

⬇ Drop files here

11. Upload Proof of Costs

Upload your financial proof of costs (Invoices etc.) in a zip. file.

⬇ Drop files here

Submit

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